

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY IN SOCIETY AND THE ROLE OF THE CONCEPT OF PUBLIC SECURITY IN IT

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Abstract: In the article, the socio-philosophical aspects of ensuring information security in the society, its necessity, the fact that it is an actual issue today, and the role of the concept of public security in this process are analyzed. The role of information technologies in public safety is explained in detail. In addition, conclusions and suggestions on increasing the role of information technologies in public security have been developed.

Key words: information, information society, integration, globalization, internet, computer, electronics, cybernetics, social, philosophical, public security, concept, information security.

As part of the large-scale reforms implemented in our country, special attention is being paid to ensuring a peaceful and peaceful life of the population and forming a culture of obedience to the law and public safety in our society. In particular, completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing work in the direction of public safety on the basis of the principle of "Serving the interests of the people" were introduced, and mutual purposeful cooperation of state bodies with public structures was established. At the same time, various dangers and conflicts that are intensifying in the world, threats to the peace and tranquility of the country, pandemics, natural and man-made disasters, state bodies responsible for their activities with the priority of "All efforts for human dignity" is tasked with further improvement based on the idea.

Although the term "information society" began to be used when computerization became widespread and information and digital technologies began to actively develop, the concept of "information society" appeared in the 1940s with the emergence of cybernetics. This concept was used in the works of American scientists K. Shannon, N. Wiener, D. von Neumann, English thinker and cryptographer A. Turing, Russian mathematician A. N. Kolmogorov, Kisho Kurokawa and Tadao Umesao, T. Umesao and F. Machhlup.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 PF-6196- The concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved in accordance with Decree No.

The processes of global information globalization require not only the introduction of information and communication technologies into the economy and other sectors of countries, but also the provision of security of information systems. The following are the main tasks in the provision of public safety in the conditions of the information society:

- effective organizational and software that ensures the collection, analysis and collection of information on current threats to information security, the prevention of illegal access to information systems, resources and databases of state bodies development of recommendations and proposals for operational adoption of technical solutions;

- coordinating the activities of state bodies and other organizations on issues of prevention of violations in the field of information and communication technologies;

- cooperation with operators and providers of telecommunication networks, law enforcement agencies in the analysis and identification of law breakers, methods and tools used in the implementation of unauthorized or disruptive actions in the information space;

- certification of information objects in accordance with current legislation;

- assistance to state bodies in the development and implementation of the information security policy of information systems and resources;

- development of suggestions on improving the regulatory legal framework in the field of ensuring information security of state information systems, resources and databases, as well as the national segment of the Internet;

- establishment of a single duty-dispatching service and data processing centers to increase the efficiency and speed of activity in the field of public safety and law enforcement;

- organization of international cooperation in the field of prevention and maintenance of information security and public law order in accordance with the established tasks

to do

The Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important document defining the state policy in the field of public safety, which is considered one of the main directions of national security.

Public security is a state of protection of the society against illegal aggressions, social and interethnic conflicts, emergency situations and other

threats, which serves the sustainable development of society and ensures the realization of human rights, freedoms and legitimate interests;

ensuring public safety - a comprehensive system that includes political, socio-economic, legal and other complex organizational measures established by the state to protect society from threats and continuously improved.

The main directions of the state policy in the field of public safety are as follows:

development and implementation of comprehensive measures to eliminate threats to public safety, including adoption of comprehensive targeted programs and ensuring their implementation;

ensuring protection of society from illegal aggressions, including early prevention of such aggressions, identification and elimination of their main factors;

prevention of social and ethnic conflicts;

identifying and stopping all forms of terrorist and extremist activity, corruption, narcotics and psychotropic substances, weapons, ammunition, explosives, illegal migration and human trafficking, and crimes and violations against human rights and freedoms fight against;

ensuring continuous and safe operation of social infrastructure, including tourism facilities;

prevention of damage and death caused by traffic accidents by improving transport infrastructure, safety standards of vehicles and traffic rules;

recidivism by citizens of this category through the socialization of persons who are prone to committing crimes, who have been placed under administrative and probation control and who have lost their way under the influence of alien ideas, including their extensive involvement in vocational training and entrepreneurship to prevent it from happening;

to protect the population and territories from natural and man-made emergency situations, to form and continuously improve the skills of the population in civil protection, fire safety;

education of minors and young people in the spirit of love for the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, prevention of offenses among them by carrying out activities aimed at protecting them from terrorism, extremism, violence and cruelty;

wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies and systems in the field of maintaining public order, ensuring the safety of citizens and fighting crime;

to ensure the constant readiness of the forces and means of the competent state bodies involved in public security, to increase their speed, to strengthen their material and technical support, as well as to increase the level of legal and social protection of their personnel.

Ensuring public safety is carried out in cooperation with state agencies and organizations, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, public associations, citizens and mass media.

Also, the entities that ensure public safety in the concept are the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the National Guard, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the State Security Service, the General Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development, it is noted that it consists of the Ministry of Health, local state authorities.

Self-government bodies of citizens participate in the implementation of state programs, regional and departmental programs for public safety, and also exercise public control over the implementation of legal documents in the field of public safety. Self-government bodies of citizens, non-governmental non-profit organizations and citizens can participate in ensuring public security by providing assistance and necessary assistance to subjects that directly provide public security.

Threats to the provision of public safety, their status and development trends, the state of public safety provision are assessed on the basis of established indicators. Public safety is provided by targeted and targeted programs, development of public safety system development strategies and their systematic implementation.

Modern forms and methods of work organization and advanced information and communication technologies are required to be widely introduced in the activities of public safety.

Conclusion

The information security system closely connects the state policy in the information field with the state policy of ensuring national security in the country. In this case, the information security system unites the main organizers of state policy into a single whole. This determines the role of information security and its position in the country's national security system. The integrity of the goals reflecting the national interests of Uzbekistan in the field of information, the strategic directions of their achievement and the systems of

their implementation means the state information policy. One of the urgent issues is to create conditions that allow the implementation of state policy in the field of information security, to support the country's economic and scientific-technical development, and to create methods and means of information protection. The final result of the implementation of the concept is the effective implementation of a qualitatively new system of ensuring public safety, peace and tranquility of the population, and the introduction of reliable and effective mechanisms for ensuring the safety of individuals, society and the state.

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